

Estimated precision at FCC-ee on measurements of tau properties, lepton universality and searches for lepton flavour violation

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Abstract

We estimate the precision at FCC-ee on the measurements of the tau mass, lifetime, leptonic branching fractions, and on the searches for lepton-flavour-violating branching fractions $\tau \rightarrow \mu\gamma$ and $\tau \rightarrow 3\mu$. We compute the estimated lepton flavour universality tests, considering the 2nd-order QED radiative corrections and estimating the radiative corrections uncertainties.

1 Tau mass

Recently, the Belle II collaboration reported the most precise measurement of the tau mass, $1777.09 \pm 0.08 \pm 0.11 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ [6]. The systematic uncertainties have been substantially reduced with respect to the previous B -factories' measurements, and the total uncertainty is smaller than the uncertainties of the measurements performed at the tau pair production threshold [3, 8]. The Belle II statistical uncertainty of $0.08 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ (45 ppm) has been obtained with $175 \cdot 10^6$ tau pairs (1901/fbof integrated luminosity), and could be improved to 1.3 ppm with $2.0 \cdot 10^{11}$ tau pairs at FCC-ee, without taking into account the larger efficiency that can be expected at FCC-ee from the comparison of LEP versus B -factories tau measurements. Rescaling the statistical uncertainty of the OPAL tau mass measurement [2] to number of Z decays expected at FCC-ee gives an estimated statistical precision of 0.9 ppm. The Belle II leading systematic uncertainty of $0.07 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ (39 ppm) is related to the knowledge of the beam energy, and is expected to be significantly smaller at FCC-ee, where the beam energy can be known with 1 ppm precision. The other Belle II leading systematic uncertainty of $0.06 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ (34 ppm) is related to the understanding of the charged tracks reconstructed momentum scale, which can probably be calibrated with 2 ppm precision at FCC-ee by matching the measured J/ψ mass to its world average, presently known to 2 ppm. Belle II reports systematics related to the estimator bias ($0.03 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), to the choice of the fit function of the pseudo-mass distribution ($0.02 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), to the detector material ($0.03 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), and to the modeling of ISR, FSR and tau decay ($0.02 \text{ MeV}/c^2$), for a total of 29 ppm. We expect that these systematics may be reduced by a factor 3 to 10 ppm at FCC-ee, which we take as the estimated precision of the measurement of the tau mass at FCC-ee. Figure 1a reports the present and future expected experimental uncertainties on the tau mass.

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Figure 1: Present and future expected experimental uncertainties on the tau mass and lifetime. The dates of the future measurements are speculative and mainly chosen for plotting purposes.

2 Tau lifetime

With a sample of $6 \cdot 10^{12}$ Z decays, it is convenient to measure the tau lifetime on the relatively small sub-sample of tau pairs where both tau leptons decay into a 3-prong topology, like Belle did [11]. For these events, the two 3-prong vertices and the constraint of the very small luminous region precisely define the tau leptons' flight directions, significantly reducing systematics from Monte Carlo simulation of the effects of the undetected neutrinos on the reconstruction of the tau flight directions.

We consider as the baseline for extrapolating to the FCC sample the DELPHI tau lifetime measurement [20], which includes a measurement done on tau pairs both decaying to 3 charged tracks (3-3-prongs topology). The DELPHI measurement is performed on the 1991-1995 sample, corresponding to about $4.0 \cdot 10^6$ hadronic Z decays [5], hence about $N_Z^{\text{DELPHI 2004}} = 4.0 \cdot 10^6 / 70\% = 5.7 \cdot 10^6$ Z decays. The statistical uncertainty on the tau lifetime with all 3-prong events is 2.4 fs, using $N_{1-3} = 15427$ 3-prong vs. 1-prong tau pairs, where only the 3-prong decay length is measured, and $N_{3-3} = 2101$ 3-prong vs. 3-prong tau pairs. By scaling we obtain the statistical uncertainty of just the 3-prong vs. 3-prong samples as:

$$\sigma(\tau_\tau, 3-3) = 2.4 \text{ fs} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{N_{1-3} + 2 \cdot N_{3-3}}{2 \cdot N_{3-3}}} \simeq 5.19 \text{ fs} = 18000 \text{ ppm} , \quad (1)$$

using the 2025 world-average tau lifetime. At DELPHI (and in general at LEP experiments) the beam spot size and the transverse impact parameter resolution are comparable with the mean transverse tau lifetime, while at FCC we expect to have significantly better experimental conditions that make the above parameters negligible with respect to the tau transverse lifetime. Taking this into account, we estimate the FCC statistical uncertainty on the tau lifetime measurement using 3-prong vs. 3-prong tau pairs as $\sigma(\tau_\tau, 3-3, \text{FCC}) = 15.0 \text{ ppm}$ [19].

The DELPHI 2004 quoted systematics due to background, reconstruction bias and vertex detector alignment (4500 ppm) can be expected to be reduced to 3.9 ppm by scaling the statistics of Z decays from the DELPHI measurement to FCC. Regarding alignment, past studies [21] indicate that the measurement of the tau lifetime, when measured in the transverse plane, is unaffected at first order by the vertex detector alignment, and in particular from the length scale of the radial positions of the vertex detector sensitive elements

The tau lifetime uncertainty due to the understanding of the absolute length scale of the detectors (typically, the strip or pixel average spacing of the vertex detector) has been assumed to be 100 ppm at LEP. At FCC-ee, this uncertainty might be reduced to 5 ppm using optical interferometric techniques developed for the MUOnE experiment [9, 10].

Figure 2: Present and future expected experimental uncertainties on the tau leptonic branching fractions. The dates of the future measurements are speculative and mainly chosen for plotting purposes.

Figure 3: Lepton universality test using the tau mass, lifetime and leptonic branching fractions measurements. The test using the measurements reported in PDG 2024 is reported in yellow (lighter), and the estimated test at FCC-ee is reported in blue (darker). B'_e denotes the average between the measured branching fraction $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow e^- \bar{\nu}_\mu \nu_\tau)$ and its Standard Model prediction using the measured branching fraction $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu \nu_\tau)$.

Additional systematics contributions are not expected to scale with statistics. At FCC, the center-of-mass energy will be known with a 1 ppm precision at FCC [1], contributing to an uncertainty of the same size. The radiated energy in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow Z^0 \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ process is estimated with a Monte Carlo simulation, and it contributes a systematic uncertainty of 350 ppm to the DELPHI 2004 tau lifetime measurement. We optimistically speculate that an improvement of a factor 30 may be achieved, reducing the related uncertainty on the tau lifetime to 11.5 ppm at FCC. We expect that the tau mass uncertainty will be reduced from ~ 50 ppm in 2025 to 9–10 ppm with future measurements either at a charm-tau factory or at FCC-ee, contributing a ~ 10 ppm uncertainty on the tau lifetime.

In conclusion, the total estimated uncertainty on the tau lifetime measurement at FCC-ee is therefore 22.3 ppm. Figure 1b reports the present and future expected experimental uncertainties on the tau lifetime.

3 Tau leptonic branching fractions

ALEPH measured the τ leptonic branching fractions $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu \nu_\tau)$ and $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow e^- \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\tau)$ with 0.44% precision (0.40% stat., 0.19% syst.) using 5.9×10^6 Z decays. Scaling to 6×10^{12} Z decays at FCC-ee yields a statistical precision of 4.1 ppm. Given the measurement's complexity, we assume the ALEPH systematic uncertainty can be reduced by a factor of 10 to 0.019%. Assuming this uncertainty is 100% correlated between the muon and electron channels, it would define the expected precision at FCC-ee. Figure 2 reports the present and future expected experimental uncertainties on the tau leptonic branching fractions.

4 Lepton universality test with the tau leptonic branching fractions

Figure 3 reports the precision of the lepton universality test using the PDG 2024 measurements compared with the test that will be possible at FCC-ee with the estimated precision of the measurements of the tau mass, tau lifetime and tau leptonic branching fractions.

5 Tests of lepton flavour universality

In order to test lepton flavour universality (LFU), we use the expression for the partial width of a heavier lepton \mathcal{L} decay to a lighter lepton ℓ

$$\Gamma[\mathcal{L} \rightarrow \nu_{\mathcal{L}}\ell\bar{\nu}_{\ell}(\gamma)] = \frac{G_{\mathcal{L}}G_{\ell}m_{\mathcal{L}}^5}{192\pi^3} f^{\mathcal{L}\ell} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\mathcal{L}\ell}), \quad (2)$$

where $f^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ is a phase space factor that depends on the leptons' masses, $\delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ and $\delta R_W^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ correspond to the QED and electroweak (EW) radiative corrections, respectively. In the HFLAV 2023 report, as in previous papers, the leading-order (LO) QED correction in α_{QED} has been used,

$$\delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell} = \frac{\alpha(m_{\mathcal{L}})}{2\pi} \left(\frac{25}{4} - \pi^2 \right). \quad (3)$$

Here, we rely on the QED radiative corrections that have been evaluated for the muon decay [15],

$$\delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell} = H_1^{\mathcal{L}\ell} \frac{\alpha(m_{\mathcal{L}})}{\pi} + H_2^{\mathcal{L}\ell} \frac{\alpha^2(m_{\mathcal{L}})}{\pi^3} + H_3^{\mathcal{L}\ell} \frac{\alpha^3(m_{\mathcal{L}})}{\pi^3} \quad (4)$$

$$H_1^{\mathcal{L}\ell} = \frac{25}{8} - \frac{\pi^2}{2} - (9 + 4\pi^2 + 12 \ln \rho) \rho + 16\pi^2 \rho^{3/2} \quad (5)$$

$$H_2^{\mathcal{L}\ell} = \frac{156815}{5184} - \frac{518}{81}\pi^2 - \frac{895}{36}\zeta(3) + \frac{67}{720}\pi^4 + \frac{53}{6}\pi^2 \ln 2 + H_{2,\text{had}}^{\mathcal{L}\ell} - \frac{5}{4}\pi^2 \sqrt{\rho}, \quad (6)$$

where $\rho = \rho^{\mathcal{L}\ell} = m_{\ell}^2/m_{\mathcal{L}}^2$, $H_{2,\text{had}}^{\mu e} = -0.042 \pm 0.002$, $H_3^{\mu e} = -15.3 \pm 2.3$, and the modified minimal subtraction scheme has been used. Since $H_2^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ and $H_3^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ have not been evaluated for the τ , we will omit them in the following in order to get partial next-to-leading-order (NLO) QED corrections for the τ leptonic decays. The code `alphaQEDr23.f` [17] has been used to compute $\alpha(m_{\tau})$. Table 1 reports the LFU-tests' coupling ratios, which have negligible differences when changing from LO to NLO QED radiative corrections. We estimate that the coupling ratios uncertainty has contributions from the present uncertainty on the τ mass in the phase space factors (1.3 ppm), from the uncertainty on $\alpha(m_{\tau})$ (0.3 ppm), and from the omission of $H_2^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ and $H_3^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ (up to 2.4 ppm, assuming that the two terms may be up to 20 times larger for the τ with respect to the muon).

Table 1: Charged weak current coupling ratios with LO and NLO QED radiative corrections. The expressions $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ correspond to the τ leptonic branching fractions.

	LO $\delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$	NLO $\delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$
$\left(\frac{g_{\tau}}{g_{\mu}}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau e} \tau_{\mu} m_{\mu}^5 f^{\mu e} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\mu e}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\mu e})}{\mathcal{B}_{\mu e} \tau_{\tau} m_{\tau}^5 f^{\tau e} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\tau e}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\tau e})}}$	1.0016 ± 0.0014	1.0016 ± 0.0014
$\left(\frac{g_{\tau}}{g_e}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau \mu} \tau_{\mu} m_{\mu}^5 f^{\mu e} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\mu e}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\mu e})}{\mathcal{B}_{\mu e} \tau_{\tau} m_{\tau}^5 f^{\tau \mu} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\tau \mu}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\tau \mu})}}$	1.0018 ± 0.0014	1.0017 ± 0.0014
$\left(\frac{g_{\mu}}{g_e}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau \mu} f^{\tau e} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\tau e}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\tau e})}{\mathcal{B}_{\tau e} f^{\tau \mu} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\tau \mu}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\tau \mu})}}$	1.0002 ± 0.0011	1.0001 ± 0.0011

6 Search for $\tau \rightarrow \mu\gamma$

To estimate the background contamination for the $\tau \rightarrow \mu\gamma$ channel at the FCC-ee, a Monte Carlo simulation was performed using a sample equivalent to 7×10^{10} visible Z decays, then extrapolated to a target of 3×10^{12} Z decays [13, 14]. Assuming realistic reconstruction and selection efficiencies, an initial sensitivity of 2×10^{-9} was projected. In the Gaussian approximation, this sensitivity corresponds to a signal yield equivalent to a 2σ fluctuation of the expected background [12]. Here, we recalculate this sensitivity as an expected upper limit at 90% confidence level (CL) for a higher-statistics sample of 6×10^{12} Z decays at FCC-ee:

$$\mathcal{B}(\tau \rightarrow \mu\gamma) < 2.0 \times 10^{-9} \cdot \frac{qN \left[1 - \frac{1}{2}(1 - 90\%) \right]}{2} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3 \times 10^{12}}}{\sqrt{6 \times 10^{12}}} \simeq 1.2 \times 10^{-9} \quad \text{at 90\% CL,} \quad (7)$$

where $qN(p)$ represents the quantile function (the inverse of the cumulative distribution function $pN(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x dN(x')dx'$) of the standard Normal distribution $dN(x)$.

7 Search for $\tau \rightarrow \mu\mu\mu$

The BelleII collaboration recently established a 90% CL upper limit of 1.9×10^{-8} for the lepton-flavor-violating branching fraction $\mathcal{B}(\tau \rightarrow \mu\mu\mu)$ [7]. This result utilized 390×10^6 τ -pairs, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 424 fb^{-1} . The selection efficiency for this search is approximately 20.4%, a significant improvement over the 7.6% efficiency achieved in the previous Belle search [16]. This performance is comparable to the 24.5% efficiency reported by DELPHI for $\tau \rightarrow \mu\gamma$ at LEP 1 [4], which was roughly four times higher than the efficiency achieved by BABAR for the same channel [18]. Assuming an optimized selection efficiency of 35.0% at FCC-ee, we project the expected sensitivity as:

$$\text{UL}_{\text{exp}}^{90} = 1.8 \times 10^{-8} \frac{20.4\%}{35.0\%} \frac{390 \times 10^6}{2.0 \times 10^{11}} = 2.0 \times 10^{-11}. \quad (8)$$

This projection is derived by linearly scaling the expected BelleII 90% CL limit (1.8×10^{-8}) to the anticipated FCC-ee statistics of 2.0×10^{11} τ -pairs. This scaling assumes that the search remains signal-limited rather than background-limited, leveraging the high-purity muon identification and clean experimental environment at the Z peak.

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